

ISic0462

I.Sicily inscription 0462

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Ilenia Gradante,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 270

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

1. [---]ane filia I[---]

2. [---][a]nnis XV[---][---]

3. [---][d]ies XV R[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491690

EDCS 21900525

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7184 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650770>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0462. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4337523>